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Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Specialized Hospital: A Journey of Transformation

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Abstract:

On Tuesday, December 5th, 2024, Dr. Noha Nabeeh sat in her office, excited and anxious, waiting for her first cancer patient—a milestone in her goal to establish a dedicated division for cancer care. Her day began like any other: she reviewed the tasks assigned to her staff, addressed patient issues with her nurses, and carefully followed up on every detail that others might skip. Known for her compassion and thoroughness, Dr. Noha was deeply involved in all aspects of her work, from reviewing patient reports to staying on top of the latest cases.

After completing her morning routine, she ended the day by interviewing two candidates for customer service center positions on the night shift. Though recruiting wasn't technically part of her role, she knew that until the hospital found the right HR Director, she would need to step in and oversee every detail.

Since being promoted to Hospital General Manager in October 2023, Dr. Noha has faced several challenges: limited financial resources, unclear strategic goals, a lack of organizational structure, and low team motivation. Yet, she was undiscouraged. She thrived on challenges and was determined to turn things around.

Was it realistic for her to overcome these obstacles and position the hospital for success in the healthcare sector? Could she lead it to compete with B-class and even A-class hospitals, all while delivering high-quality medical care at affordable prices for middle-class and low-income patients?

Keywords: Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Specialized Hospital, Transformation

Overview about Healthcare in Egypt

The Egyptian healthcare system consists of both public and private sectors. The government covers the basic healthcare needs of everyone. Additionally, people who can afford it can also get private services. Four different sources of money support the system: the government, the public sector, private organizations, and donations from people and families.

The Ministry of Health runs hospital centers that offer free health services as part of public healthcare. The Health Insurance Organization (HIO) and the Curative Care Organization (CCO) pay for most public healthcare, but the HIO is the largest payer. They cover around 60% of the population by deducting fees from workers' and employers' paychecks. The Health Insurance Organization (HIO) operates its network of medical facilities and, at times, contracts with private healthcare providers. The Curative Care Organization (CCO) offers inpatient and outpatient care in specific governorates through agreements with other entities and individuals. Additionally, many mosques and churches operate their own subsidized or free clinics, especially in large cities.

There are also private insurance options and a network of private healthcare providers and medical facilities. The private sector includes for-profit clinics, hospitals, and pharmacies. People believe that public healthcare is inferior to private healthcare in terms of quality of service. Only 4.75% of Egypt's GDP is dedicated to investments in healthcare services. Almost half of the public healthcare facilities have shortages

of medical equipment and personnel. It is presumed that only 20% of the 660 government hospitals are committed to safety and infection control standards. Only about 6% of Egyptians covered by the Health Insurance Organization utilize its services due to dissatisfaction with the level of services it funds. In 2007/2008, 60% of health expenditure in Egypt was paid out of pocket by people seeking treatment. Excessive reliance on out-of-pocket financing of medical treatments creates inequalities in healthcare access. In 2007, more than a fifth of the population struggled with catastrophic healthcare-related payments.

The healthcare system in Egypt, a lower-middle-income country with a population of approximately 102 million as of 2020, involves multiple stakeholders, including public and private healthcare providers, as well as several financing agents. Over the past decade, the Egyptian healthcare system has shown improvement in several aspects, despite its challenges. By 2006, 95% of the population had access to primary healthcare within 5 km, and 98% of citizens were offered vaccinations.

Despite improvements in health statistics, such as an increase in life expectancy from 64.5 to 70.5 years, healthcare financing remains a challenge. The Total Health Expenditure (THE) in Egypt, as a percentage of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), has remained relatively stable, ranging between 3.0% and 7.0% over the past 12 years, with a median of 5.5%. However, the precise figures, THE has been increasing, indicating a growth in healthcare spending in the Egyptian economy. Governmental Health Expenditure (GHE) accounts for approximately one-third of THE, varying from 24.8% to 50% of THE. It represents about 3.0% to 7.3% of the GDP and around 6.8% of the government budget. This expenditure has increased over the years, with recent figures showing an expenditure of about 73 billion EGP for the year 2019-2020.

The Egyptian government is moving towards implementing the Universal Health Insurance (UHI) project, with a phased implementation planned to be completed by 2032. On 11 January 2018, the Ministry of Health and Population launched the National Health Insurance project and increased its expenditure on healthcare services. It is a new mandatory health insurance system in Egypt, operating under Law No. 2 of 2018, to provide comprehensive healthcare coverage to the entire population. It aims to reduce financial healthcare expenses, increase the public funding proportion, and replace the current health insurance system gradually through diffusing into the country's control. Its umbrella covers all citizens participating in the system. Universal Health Insurance differs from the Health Insurance Organization in that the family will be considered the central unit of insurance coverage within the system. Another difference is that Universal Health Insurance is based on separating funding from service provision, and the Universal Health Insurance Authority may not provide treatment services or participate in providing them. Still, its role is to contract different health care providers (public or private) to provide services for the insured citizens.

Noha's Unwavering Determination in Managing Her Career:

It had been two years since Dr. Noha Nabeeh left Al-Rahma Hospital to join Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Specialized Hospital as the Medical Director in 2021. Two years later, she was promoted to general manager for the hospital. She was a very ambitious clinical pharmacist who had previous experience in several non-profit healthcare institutions.

Dr. Noha Nabeeh, the general manager of the hospital, completed a six-month clinical pharmacy course at Al Qasr Al Aini Hospital at Cairo University School of Medicine in 2003. She was determined to fulfill her role as a clinical pharmacist and make a significant impact on her career. This training prepared her to work closely with medical professionals to ensure that patients receive the correct prescriptions in the appropriate amounts, considering their individual needs and health status.

Noha, in 2013, along with five other pharmacists from her previous job at Nasr City Hospital, chose to accept this challenge to become a clinical pharmacologist out of a total of fifty. Under the direction of Dr. Azza Moharam, who was then in charge of the Clinical Pharmacy Department, they collaborated to implement clinical pharmacy procedures at Nasr City Hospital. This was the first step in her career development process.

The Head of the Health Insurance Authority requested that Dr. Noha take on the role of Pharmacist Manager of Chemotherapy at the soon-to-open Nasr City Oncology Center, a brand-new, five-floor building still under construction. In record time, she and her small team of five clinical pharmacists began equipping the center from scratch with the donations and subsidies of pharmaceutical companies, and it started operations in 2014. Noha was able to succeed in meeting her first milestone in developing her career.

Noha Assigned as Medical Director for Rahma Hospital:

Noha Nabeeh was once again elected and nominated by the Ministry of Health in 2019. Dr. Ahmed Emad issued a decree allowing pharmacists to fill medical director roles—a post formerly designated only for physicians. Noha Nabeeh was assigned to take on the responsibility of another non-profit healthcare institution at Al Rahma Hospital, which marked another milestone for her as the medical director of the hospital, following her success in her previous role at Nasr Hospital. The exceptional contributions made by Dr. Noha to the Nasr City Oncology Center and her position in clinical pharmacy led to her being chosen as the medical director at El-Rahma Hospital. Dr. Noha rose to be Egypt's first pharmacist bearing this title.

She served as the medical director of El-Rahma Hospital for four years, from 2019 to 2022. Throughout this period, she achieved considerable success at the hospital. The number of beds in the intensive care unit went from 14 to 30. She established a system for tracking costs, successfully turning the hospital's losses into profits in 2020. Additionally, she transferred the hospital's outsourcing pharmacy to the hospital's management and supervision, which led to an increase in the facility's revenue.

It was not easy for Noha to become a medical director at the hospital. Her nomination for this position was opposed by the physicians at the hospital, who believed that only a physician could run the hospital, not a clinical pharmacist. She took it upon herself to meet with all the physicians who opposed her nomination for the medical director job. Clinical Pharmacists were able to assess the status of the patient's health problems and determine whether the prescribed medications optimally met the patient's needs and goals of care. Evaluate the appropriateness and effectiveness of the patient's medications. She was known for her emotional intelligence, patience, and sense of endurance. Eventually, the physicians began to request that the clinical pharmacists accompany them when they visited patients on their rounds at the hospital.

Noha's character was the type that could not stay still; she was always caring for others and helping those who needed help. This was her way of helping as many people as possible, the only difference being that she would serve the needy patients who were unable to receive proper medical attention due to the financial burdens of the healthcare sector. Noha worked in tandem with medical professionals to ensure that patients received the correct prescriptions with the right medicine doses while considering their health status.

Noha as the New GM for al Kholafaa El Rashideen specialized Hospital:

In January 2023, Dr. Noha was chosen to achieve her third milestone in her career development. Although she was assigned as the medical director in 2023, the new board of directors promoted her to hospital general manager at Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen ten months later, in October of that year. This was a fast-track promotion, the most challenging of her career. Despite her considerable accomplishments at El-Rahma, Dr. Noha pursued new challenges and sought greater opportunities for impact. At Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen, she discovered a board of directors that offered support, a team of committed staff, and opportunities to expand the hospital's potential.

Challenges The GM Has to Face and Deal With:

Although she had the support of the board, she faced numerous challenges. To begin with, there was a lack of explicit objectives and plans, along with inadequate compensation, which led to a deterioration in employee morale. Crucial departments, such as human resources and public relations, were missing, and the lack of night shift coverage resulted in several patient complaints. The hospital's management also relied significantly on centralized decision-making, which led to employees feeling untrusted and disengaged.

Dr. Noha prioritized the establishment of a Human Resources department to clearly define job roles and career paths for the staff. She occupied crucial roles within the hospital's framework and launched training initiatives centered on infection control and quality standards.

She embedded the concepts of teamwork and patient-centeredness into the hospital's culture, which aided her application for employee empowerment.

She initiated an internship program and devised a creative approach to attract new talent to the hospital. Recognizing the importance of teamwork, she established a system for collaboration and recruited talented individuals from her previous teams at various hospitals to contribute to the hospital's transformation. She was also eager to meet with the doctors once a week and with the staff once more.

Dr. Noha set Goals and Objectives for the hospital. One of the hospital's essential objectives in 2024 is to obtain Accreditation from the General Authority for Health Accreditation and Control (GAHAR). This Accreditation helps enhance safety and quality standards in healthcare institutions, leading to improved patient experiences and increased trust in the services provided. Standards set by GAHAR improve the overall performance of hospitals and health centers, diminish medical errors, and raise operational efficiency. In addition, accreditation strengthens the reputation of any healthcare organization because the commitment to quality standards demonstrates the trust of patients and healthcare providers in these associations. Accreditation also urges healthcare professionals to improve their skills and awareness to align with the Authority's needs, eventually upgrading the level of professionalism in these healthcare institutions.

Noha was able to increase the profit, despite her budget rising from 33 million EGP to 55 million, with a 10% profit instead of a 5% profit. With an anticipated profit of 13–14%, the earliest indicators now amount to 80 million EGP. However, Noha knew she had a lot to work on, as she faced numerous challenges and obstacles to overcome for this year and for years to come. The hospital operated with a dedicated team of 131 employees, 37 on-call doctors, and 65 nurses and assistants.

This workforce ensured the smooth delivery of medical and administrative services across all departments, meeting the needs of over 100,000 patients during the period from October 2023 to December 2024. Will she be able to meet all these challenges and overcome the obstacles? Will she be able to achieve the same level of success she had in Al Rahma Hospital again in Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen?

Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Specialized Hospital History:

Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Specialized Hospital, located in Al-Sabaq Street in Heliopolis, Cairo, and owned by Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Association, began its medical operations with outpatient clinics, an X-ray lab, and a kidney dialysis unit in the 1970s. The hospital was officially licensed on 1 November 1984, to provide maternity services and minor to intermediate general surgeries. Operations continued in this capacity until the early 2000s, after which the hospital ceased functioning. It remained closed until the Minister of Social Solidarity took over the hospital from the Ministry of Justice in January 2016 and delegated the Holding Company to manage and operate the hospital's care services. But things changed significantly after the Minister of Social Solidarity decided to create a new board of directors for the association. This decision followed official rules and legal steps to help the hospital improve and move forward.

On January 10, 2016, an administrative decree, No. 14, was issued to form the first Board of Directors of the Association, consisting of Prof. Dr. Hisham Atta, Prof. Dr. Ahmed Safaan, Mr. Ashraf Khairy, Prof. Dr. Rana Zeidan, and Prof. Dr. Kamal Sherif. This board, under the leadership of the hospital's General Manager at the time, Dr. Hisham Zazou, initiated the development and shift in administrative thinking.

Then, Decree No. 73 was issued on 2 March 2021 to form the current Board of Directors, consisting of Prof. Dr. Abdelwahab Ezzat, Prof. Dr. Ahmed Safaan, Prof. Dr. Rana Zeidan, Mr. Gamal Abdel Nasser, and Eng. Nehad Shelbaya, a distinguished and well-pronounced professor and physician, along with Dr. Hisham Zazou, as the executive director of the association and a member of the current board.

The development continued under the current board, led by Dr. Noha Nabeeh, the new Hospital General Manager.

The Association Activities:

The medical activities of the hospital include an operating unit with three large rooms for surgeries, a kidney dialysis unit, and a blood storage bank. The hospital had an Integrated Radiation Center furnished with (MRI, CT, Mammogram, Nerve Drawing, Stress Echocardiography, Panoramic X-Ray, Doppler imaging, Ultrasound, Brain imaging, and Ordinary Digital Radiology). There is also an analysis laboratory and a physiotherapy center. The internal section of the hospital consists of (29) beds, as well as an intensive care unit with (14) beds, and an additional intensive care section with (5) beds.

The Association also engages in educational and community activities to support society as well as to support the charitable part of the hospital. The educational activities include a villa converted into a nursery, which was rented on January 1, 2024, at a monthly rent of 30,000 Egyptian pounds. The association also manages two schools for the same purpose. The first is the Om El Momineen, Mrs. Aisha School, which is administered by the 30 June Schools Board of the Ministry of Education. This school is leased under a renewed three-year contract starting January 1, 2024, with an annual rental value of 2,657,341.5 EGP and a 10% annual increase. The second is the Lighthouse School, which is being under construction alongside Om El Momineen, Aisha School in El-Obour.

Hospital Renovation and Development Projects:

The hospital's renovation began in January 2016, led by the first Board of Directors of the Association under the guidance of Dr. Hisham Zazou, the General Manager of the hospital at that time. It started with three public tenders for three main projects aimed at fully operating the hospital. The improvements included the construction of a new staircase (for 540,540 EGP) and elevator (allowing trolley access for 221,480 EGP) to connect all hospital components efficiently across four floors (120 m² each), along with the construction of a Back-Passage Walkway (300 m²) and a new gate on Rafaha Al-Tahtawi Street. To upgrade the hospital's infrastructure, new public and sub-electrical distribution panels were installed, along with an Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) unit, which ensures a consistent power supply to connected devices, an emergency panel, and a new electrical generator at a cost of 385,000 EGP.

Additionally, a new entrance ramp was developed to improve ambulance access for hospital services. The initial phase of development covered a total area of 1,500 m² on the first floor, including:

- Surgeries Suite: 3 surgery rooms over an area of 230 m².
- Recovery Suite: 18 beds covering an area of 230 m².
- Intensive Care Unit (ICU): 14 beds over an area of 330 m².
- Diagnostic Radiology and Laboratory Department: a comprehensive medical analysis lab within an area of 350 m².

The entire development process, completed through a general tender, cost approximately 10 million Egyptian pounds. (Exhibit 4)

Achievements Under the Current Board in March 2021 with Dr. Noha as the General Manager:

The current Board of Directors of Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen, led by Dr. Noha Nabeeh as General Manager, has achieved outstanding milestones in several departments since its establishment in March 2021, demonstrating a strong commitment to expansion and high-quality treatment.

New facilities were built in two stages, with the first floor housing 11 beds and the second floor housing 10 beds for the inpatient department. To accommodate growing patient demand, the intensive care unit (ICU) was significantly expanded with the addition of a newly constructed 14-bed ICU, and a new 5-bed ICU is currently under development. In response to particular demands from physicians and patients, a private intensive care unit was also established.

Advanced equipment, including X-ray, MRI, mammography, panoramic dental X-ray, CT scan, ultrasound, and echo machines, was installed in the Radiology Department. A specialized microbiological lab was

added, and the Laboratory's efficiency was increased. A C-Arm X-ray machine was purchased to improve the operating rooms in the Surgery Department, and new 250-liter sterilizing equipment was created for the Central Sterilizing Unit.

The outpatient clinics are presently undergoing significant renovations. The establishment of a physiotherapy center brought cutting-edge therapies, including cavitation and cryotherapy. Similarly, a dermatology center now offers basic cosmetic treatments and specialist services, such as Botox, to enhance the patient experience, attract doctors from various specialties to support the hospital, and expand the range of medical services offered. These services aim to attract middle-class patients who can afford the service at a reasonable price. Dr. Noha is aiming to allocate resources effectively, covering the expenses required to support the hospital's charitable initiatives while investing in its renovation and development.

Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Hospital utilizes effective digital and direct marketing strategies to promote its dermatology cosmetic treatments and specialized services, such as Botox. The hospital employs brochures, screens, and roll-ups to attract visitors to the clinic. Additionally, the hospital organizes events in social clubs, including 'Patients' Day,' as part of its corporate social responsibility, enhancing the overall medical experience for patients. Word of mouth plays a significant role in their marketing efforts, with visitors coming from all backgrounds, including class A. This broad client base is drawn to the high-quality services provided by university professors, which remain affordable with consultation fees ranging from 120 to 200 Egyptian pounds. Located in the heart of New Cairo, the hospital caters to cosmetic clients who prioritize excellent service at competitive prices. The presence of class A clients also contributes to the hospital's charitable initiatives, as many of these individuals support the less fortunate through the hospital's efforts.

Designated days for complimentary medical examinations were established in accordance with the hospital's commitment to corporate social responsibility (CSR) and community engagement. Local club members were identified, and senior appreciation events were organized at Al-Nasr Club, Holilido, Egypt Ladies' Club, and Flamingo Nursery. The hospital utilized worker donations and internal resources to assist patients from underprivileged households.

A blood storage bank was constructed to meet the rising demand, and plans call for obtaining licenses for the third and fourth floors, which will add more operational rooms and beds. To demonstrate compliance with quality criteria, the hospital is also aiming for GAHAR certification. The hospital's capacity was significantly boosted with the inclusion of a gastrointestinal endoscopic section.

New leadership positions, created by Noha Nabeeh, were established to ensure the delivery of premium services and streamline processes. These enhancements require roles like Internal Department Supervisor, Medical Engineering Manager, Clinics Manager, Occupational Safety and Health Manager, Quality Manager, Infection Control Manager, Medical Director, HR Director, and Evening Medical Director.

Noha also ensured the installation of a pharmacy with laminar flow equipment to guarantee safe preparation and a chemotherapy unit with four patient seats. In addition, the hospital completed nearly 9,000 dialysis treatments in 2024 through partnerships with health insurance companies. These advancements demonstrated the hospital's commitment to expansion, creativity, and providing the community with top-notch care.

Hospital Infrastructure and Safety Enhancements

To improve patient care and ensure readiness during emergencies, the hospital recently installed liquid oxygen tanks, providing a continuous 24-hour oxygen supply. This upgrade replaced traditional cylinders, which often ran low during critical times during the COVID pandemic, making it a life-saving step. Additionally, comprehensive safety and civil protection measures have been implemented, meeting all required safety standards. The hospital is expected to receive final approval for its workplace safety license soon.

Is Moving Forward Possible After All

Dr. Noha Nabeeh, the new General Manager (GM) at Al Kholafaa El Rashideen Specialized Hospital, has been a driving force in the hospital's growth and development. Despite her previous success at El-Rahma Hospital, she has faced numerous challenges, including a lack of clear objectives, inadequate compensation, and insufficient night shift coverage. To address these issues, Dr. Noha established a Human Resources department to define job roles and career paths for staff and launched training initiatives focused on infection control and quality standards.

Noha also implemented an internship program and introduced a system for sharing and hiring talented people from her previous teams. She set goals and objectives for the hospital, including obtaining accreditation from the General Authority for Health Accreditation and Control (GAHAR) in 2024.

Dr. Noha and the current board of directors have achieved significant milestones under her leadership, including the construction of new facilities, the expansion of the ICU, the installation of advanced equipment, and the renovation of outpatient clinics. The hospital has also established designated days for complimentary medical examinations, utilized worker donations and internal resources to assist patients from underprivileged households, and established a blood bank to meet the rising needs.

Noha has also created new leadership positions to ensure the delivery of premium services and simplified processes. These advancements include the installation of a pharmacy with laminar flow equipment, a chemotherapy unit, and the successful completion of almost 9,000 dialysis treatments during 2024 through partnerships with health insurance companies.

Yet, many challenges remain ahead. Noha still faces difficulties competing with A- and B-class hospitals, succeeding in the healthcare industry, and providing high-quality care to middle-class and low-income patients at reasonable costs. The question remains: can she overcome these challenges and succeed?

Exhibits:

EXHIBIT 1: Patient Services and Operations (January–November 2024)

The hospital has provided extensive services across multiple departments during this period, as summarized below:

Service Type	Total Cases
Inpatient Admissions	2,562 (including 1,988 surgeries)
Emergency Cases	11,714
Outpatient Clinics	53,484
Dialysis Sessions	8,633
ICU Admissions	1,165
Laboratory Tests	9,943
Radiology Scans	10,624
Blood Bank Services	2,687
Total Patients Served	100,812

EXHIBIT 2: Fixed assets growth (in million EGP) from base year to date (2016-2024)

Years	2016-2020	2021	2022	2023	Till Nov. 2024
Asset Balance in EGP	34.8 M	37.1 M	37.7 M	41.6 M	47.4 M

EXHIBIT 3: Cash Position and Bank Accounts (in million EGP) from 2016-2024

Years	2016-2020	2021	2022	2023	Till Nov. 2024
Cash Balance in EGP	8 M	5.9 M	4.2 M	5.1 M	7.2 M

Note: The decrease in cash balance during development, as well as the increase in fixed assets worth more than £ 20 million from 2016 to 2023, is attributed to the hospital development process.

EXHIBIT 4: Income and expenditure (as % of total) from 2016 to 2024

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Revenues (%)	4.11%	4.03%	4.30%	4.26%	6.87%	12.67%	13.66%	18.24%	31.86%
Expenses (%)	2.60%	2.95%	3.64%	4.17%	7.42%	13.84	14.62%	18.78%	31.97%

EXHIBIT 5: Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Organizational Chart in July 2024

EXHIBIT 6: Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Building Before Development

EXHIBIT 7: Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Building After Development

EXHIBIT 8: Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Nursery building Before Development

EXHIBIT 9: Al Kholafaa Al Rashideen Nursery building After Development

EXHIBIT 10: Al Obour School building under construction (Educational Activity to support Healthcare Activities)

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